

SENSORPOD: A MODULAR DEPLOYABLE INTEGRATED SENSOR SUITE FOR LUNAR SURFACE EXPLORATION. Z. Ioannou¹, M.R. Mughal² and L. Burtz³, ¹Physics Department, College of Science, Sultan Qaboos University, Muscat, Oman, ²Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering, College of Engineering, Sultan Qaboos University, Muscat, Oman, ³Lunar Vision, Japan.

Introduction: In recent years it has been demonstrated that very low cost, but high data quality lunar surface missions are now possible. The concept of utilizing such low-cost concepts was validated by JAXA's Sora-Q micro-rover, which provided critical visual data for the SLIM lander [1] as well as the YAOKI mini rover that was carried to the lunar surface by the Athena lander of the Intuitive Machines company's 2nd attempt to land successfully on the Moon. [2]

In this work, we present SensorPod, a lightweight (<500 g) and compact (< 300 cm³) solution designed to augment the data acquisition of lunar rovers, landers or hoppers. By utilizing Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) and flight-proven hardware, the platform integrates three cameras, an IMU, temperature sensors, and microphones into a versatile bus featuring a microcontroller and wireless transceiver. Additionally, the modular design allows for the inclusion of additional specialized sensors and instruments (e.g. Langmuir probes, dust sensors, etc). SensorPod can be carried by a mobile asset or deployed to operate autonomously for several hours, providing vital third-person views and characterization of the lunar environment. Its customizable sensor suite and minimal power requirements, offers a highly adaptable tool for enhancing surface operations.

Hardware & Design: The SensorPod design aims to maximize the instrumentation to structure ratio. A 3D printed prototype can be seen in Figure 1.

Outer shell & Spacecraft Adapter: SensorPod is composed of two independent parts. The main sensor suite device and an adapter that holds the sensor package fixed to the outer wall of a rover or lander. Release of the sensor suite is achieved through a burn-wire mechanism.

Electronics and CPU: Building on the success of the Sora-Q rover we employ the Sony SpreSense main board microcontroller which uses a 6-core CPU with 156 Hz clock frequency and 8 MB of flash memory. It exhibits a 2-channel analogue input and can support several digital inputs through I2C and SPI protocols. Each microcontroller has a dedicated input for a camera module. A total of 3 SpreSense microcontrollers are used. Two are found on the main sensor suite module for redundancy and one is housed on the spacecraft adapter and connected to a WiFi module for wireless communications with the sensor suite. The spacecraft adapter microcontroller can be connected to the main spacecraft (lander or

rover) either wirelessly or through a hardwire connection.

In addition to the microcontrollers, an inhouse developed multiplexer unit is also used to allow for simultaneous inputs from all the sensors and instruments.

Communication: The SensorPod sensor suite communicates with the spacecraft adapter through a WiFi/Bluetooth transceiver module. The WiFi transceiver operates at 2.4 GHz using the 802.11 b/g/n standards.

Power and Thermal: The SensorPod is powered directly from the rover or lander when attached to the spacecraft body. A 5000 mWh non-rechargeable battery (Li-SOC12) with a very low discharge rate of <1%/year is used to power the sensor suite module once it detaches itself from them spacecraft adapter. Depending on environmental and operational scenarios the battery would be able to power the sensor suite module for 2-4 hours when placed on a sunlit lunar surface region.

Passive thermal management is used in the form of Kapton-mylar multi-layer insulation blanket for when the sensor suite is deployed onto the lunar surface. When attached to the host spacecraft during flight or before deployment a heater is utilized to keep the temperature of the SensorPod components within operational limits.

Sensors and Instrumentation: The sensor suite module utilizes a number of COTS sensors, but it can also host customized instruments such as a miniaturized Langmuir probe.

Imaging: The Sony Group SpreSense platform provides a robust ecosystem suitable for resource-constrained space applications. Perhaps more importantly the hardware has already been successfully operated in the lunar environment. The prototype detailed in this study integrates an almost fully panoramic camera vision system leveraging three specialized Sony modules: the standard 5.0 Megapixel (MP) camera and the High Dynamic Range (HDR) camera. The 5 MP module utilizes the ISX012 sensor, yielding high-resolution imagery at 2608 x 1960 pixels, which is ideal for detailed morphological analysis of the lunar surface. The HDR camera employs the ISX019 sensor with a resolution of 1280 x 960 pixels. The integration of HDR imaging is particularly critical for lunar surface operations, as it effectively mitigates the extreme illumination contrasts and the high dynamic range lunar shadow environment [3]. Both sensors output data with an 8-bit colour depth and utilize the I2C serial communication protocol for board-level configuration and con-

trol. Furthermore, the HDR camera module features an interchangeable lens mount, allowing for mission-specific optical customization. In the current prototype configuration, the sensors are equipped with ultra-wide-angle lenses collectively providing close to 220° Field of view (FOV).

Sensor Suite: An Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) is part of the sensor suite and used to determine motion and the orientation of the module. The IMU module consists of 16 independent, consumer-grade IMUs with each unit having a 3-axis accelerometer and a 3-axis gyroscope. Sampling rates range between 15 Hz and 960 Hz thus being able to provide high frequency data, for example during the drop deployment.

Thermometers & Microphones: A set of 6 analogue thermocouples are used to measure internal as well as an external temperature. One of the thermocouples are connected to a needle probe that can penetrate down to 5 cm below the lunar surface.

Two digital microphones placed on the bottom plate of the sensor suite unit can record vibrations of the surface (e.g. when a rover is driving by) or they can be used to listen to mechanical vibrations of the rover or lander while still attached on the host spacecraft body.

Langmuir Probe: A miniaturized Langmuir Probe (LNG) similar to the one described in [4] is under development with the University of Oslo. The instrument would be used to measure variations of photoelectron density due to changes in solar radiation and illumination conditions (e.g. shadowing by a rover or because of lunar day variations).

Concept of Operations: The highly modular architecture of the SensorPod allows a variety of operational scenarios across diverse lunar mission profiles. The payload's lifecycle can be distinctly categorized into three primary phases: attached transit and operations, autonomous surface deployment, and passive end-of-life utility.

Attached Operations - Transit to Deployment: During the launch and translunar cruise phases, the SensorPod remains predominantly dormant to conserve power, activating only for periodic telemetry and system health checks. During the critical descent and landing sequence, the payload offers operational flexibility: it can either remain powered down or be commanded to initialize, capturing high-resolution imagery and IMU telemetry of the landing event. Following the landing event, while still attached to the host spacecraft SensorPod functions as an auxiliary sensor suite. From its mounted viewpoint, it actively augments the primary spacecraft's scientific payloads and navigational awareness.

Deployment and Autonomous Operations: Upon deployment to a selected location the SensorPod physically separates from the host spacecraft by the use of a burn wire mechanism and a zero-force con-

necter that provides the wired link of the sensor suite to the spacecraft adapter is severed. Once deployed, the SensorPod transitions into a fully autonomous operational mode. It relies exclusively on its internal systems for power and data acquisition until its internal battery is exhausted.

Passive Utility Phase: Following battery depletion, the SensorPod sensor suite unit transitions into a passive experimental and/or calibration target and/or materials exposure experiment unit that may provide ongoing navigational and radiometric reference data (e.g. colour targets) for the host spacecraft imaging sensors.

References: [1] D. Hirano et al., IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters, vol. 9, 4, (2024). [2] C. Chun et al. IAC, (2025). [3] U. Wong, et al. IEEE Aerospace Conference (2020). [4] L. Clausen et al., Space Science Reviews, vol 221, 34 (2025).

Figure 1: A 3D printed prototype sensor suite unit is shown below. Two of the imaging sensors and the onboard electronics can be seen through the structure. A 3D CAD model showing the connection to the spacecraft adapter can also be seen below the image.

